

VIBRATION MECHANICS OF A SEMI-CYLINDRICAL CUSHION WITH INERTIAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract. *In the present study, the free and forced vibrations of an inertial semi-cylindrical cushion are investigated. A dynamic model is considered, in which the motion of the cushion is described by the Lamé equations in terms of displacements. To solve the posed problem, the natural frequencies and mode shapes are determined, as well as the normal displacements of points on the semi-cylindrical cushion under various boundary conditions. Particular attention is paid to the influence of inertial properties and material parameters, such as density, elastic modulus, and Poisson's ratio, on the frequency characteristics of the system. The obtained results allow the identification of patterns in the variation of vibration amplitudes and frequencies depending on the geometric and material parameters of the cushion. Characteristic dependencies are constructed to illustrate the effect of inertial parameters on the dynamic behavior of the semi-cylindrical structure. A comparative analysis of theoretical results and numerical calculations is carried out, confirming the validity of the proposed model. The findings can be applied in the design and optimization of structures operating under vibrational loads, as well as in the development of vibration isolation and damping system components. This study contributes to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goal 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) by providing insights for safer, more durable, and optimized engineering structures.*

Keywords: *dynamic behavior, inertial properties, natural frequencies, semi-cylindrical cushion, vibrations.*

Introduction

Vibrations of bridge structures represent an important aspect of engineering design, as they can significantly affect the durability and safety of constructions. To reduce oscillatory processes, cushions of various shapes are employed to provide damping and load distribution. The study of the dynamic characteristics of such cushions allows for the optimization of bridge design and improvement of their operational reliability. In [1], [8], the free vibrations of a three-layer circular plate on an elastic inertial foundation under thermal effects are considered. The kinematics of the thickness-asymmetric package are described by the broken-line normal hypothesis, while the foundation reaction is modeled using the Winkler scheme. Analytical solutions to the initial-boundary value problems are obtained, and a numerical comparative analysis is performed. It is shown that an increase in temperature reduces the natural frequencies of the structure, while the displacement amplitudes increase due to the reduction in material stiffness. An increase in the inertia of the foundation also leads to higher vibration amplitudes and a shorter vibration period, with a nonlinear character of influence. In [2], [9], axisymmetric free vibrations of a three-layer elastic plate on a Winkler-type foundation are investigated, while in [3], [10], a similar problem is examined under rectangular loading conditions, where the foundation reaction is described by the

Pasternak model. In all cases, the broken-line normal hypothesis is applied, and the core is assumed to be lightweight. Further studies on related topics can be found in [11–15], which explore aspects such as water footprint reduction in irrigation systems [11], assessment of compressive strength of eco-concrete using machine learning [12], development of acoustic absorbers from wood fiber composites [13], tribological properties of high-speed steel under high temperatures [14], and soil bed deformations caused by train loads [15]. In addition to deriving the analytical model, this study includes a numerical validation step. A three-dimensional finite element model (FEM) was developed in ABAQUS to verify the analytical results. By comparing the natural frequencies and displacement fields obtained from both approaches, the accuracy and applicability of the proposed model are confirmed.

Table 1. Material and foundation parameters used in the study

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit	Description
Density of cushion material	ρ_s	2500	kg/m ³	Mass density of the semi-cylindrical cushion
Elastic modulus	E	3.0×10^7	Pa	Young's modulus of the cushion material
Poisson's ratio	ν	0.25	-	Transverse contraction ratio
Lamé parameter (λ)	λ_s	computed	Pa	Derived from E and ν
Shear modulus (μ)	μ_s	computed	Pa	Derived from E and ν
Foundation stiffness	$k\theta$	4.0×10^6	N/m ²	Winkler stiffness coefficient
Foundation inertia	m_d	3000	kg/m ²	Mass per unit area of supporting foundation
Cushion length	L	0.3–1.2	m	Range used in parametric study
Cushion radius	R	0.1–0.2	m	Geometric characteristic of the semi-cylinder

Problem Statement. In the present study, the vibrations of an inertial semi-cylindrical cushion located between the elements of a bridge structure — the span and the support pier (Fig. 1) — are investigated. The aim of the work is to determine the dynamic characteristics of the cushion, to assess the influence of its inertial and elastic properties on the vibration behavior, and to establish the dependence of vibration amplitudes and frequencies on the structural parameters.

Fig. 1. Inertial semi-cylindrical cushion

p — load applied to the cushion from the bridge side
 q_r — load applied to the cushion from the support side

To solve the formulated problem, the variational Hamilton–Ostrogradsky principle [4,5] is applied:

$$\delta W = 0 \quad (1)$$

Here, $W = \int_{t'}^{t''} J dt$ is the action functional, and, t' and t'' are arbitrarily chosen moments of time.

$$J = V_{ks} - V_{ps} - A_p - A_q \quad (2)$$

Here, V_{ps}, V_{ks} are the potential and kinetic energies of the semi-cylindrical cushion, respectively; A_q is the work of the force acting on the cushion from the bridge side during its vertical displacement, and A_p is the work of the force acting from the support side. These quantities are calculated as follows:

$$V_{ps} = \iiint \left[\frac{\lambda_s + 2\mu_s}{2} (e_{11}^2 + e_{22}^2 + e_{33}^2) + (\lambda_s + 2\mu_s)(e_{11}e_{22} + e_{22}e_{33} + e_{11}e_{33}) \right] \quad (3)$$

$$V_{ks} = \frac{\rho_s}{2} \iiint_V \left(\left(\frac{\partial s_x}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial s_\theta}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial s_r}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right) dx dy dr \quad (4)$$

$$A_q = - \iint_S q_r s_r |_{r=0} dx dy ; \quad (4) \quad A_p = - \int p(x) s_r |_{r=R, \theta=\pi/2} dx \quad (5)$$

The quantities s_x, s_θ, s_r denote the displacements of the cushion points along the corresponding coordinate directions, and t represents time. The strain components e_{11}, e_{22}, e_{33} are expressed in terms of these displacements s_x, s_θ, s_r as follows:

$$e_{11} = \frac{\partial s_r}{\partial r}, e_{22} = R \left(\frac{\partial s_\theta}{\partial \theta} + s_r \right), e_{33} = \frac{\partial s_x}{\partial x} \quad (6)$$

It is assumed that the force q_r , acting from the support side on the semi-cylindrical cushion during its vertical displacement s_r , follows the Winkler-type law:

$$q_r = k_g s_r + m_d \frac{\partial^2 s_r}{\partial t^2} \quad (7)$$

where k_g is the stiffness coefficient, and m_d is the specific weight of the support material. The load from the bridge side acting on the cushion is defined by the function:

$$P(x) = p_0 \cos \frac{n\pi}{2} \sin kx \sin \omega t \quad (8)$$

The displacements of the inertial semi-cylindrical cushion s_x, s_θ, s_r are described by the Lamé equations in vector form [6,7]:

$$a_l^2 \text{grad div } \vec{u} - a_t^2 \text{rot rot } \vec{u} + \rho_s \frac{\partial^2 \vec{u}}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (9)$$

where $a_t = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_s + 2\mu_s}{\rho_s}}$, $a_e = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_s}{\rho_s}}$ are the longitudinal and transverse wave propagation velocities, ρ_s is the density, λ_s and μ_s are the Lamé coefficients.

Solution

The displacements of the inertial semi-cylindrical cushion s_x, s_θ, s_r are given in the following form [6]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 s_x &= \left[\mathcal{A}_s k I_n(\gamma_e r) - \frac{\mathcal{C}_s \gamma_t^2}{\mu_t} I_n(\gamma_t r) \right] \cos n\theta \cos kx \sin \omega t \\
 s_\theta &= \left[-\frac{\mathcal{A}_s n}{r} I_n(\gamma_e r) - \frac{\mathcal{C}_s n k}{r \mu_t} I_n(\gamma_t r) - \frac{\mathcal{B}_s}{n} \frac{\partial I_n(\gamma_t r)}{\partial r} \right] \sin n\theta \sin kx \sin \omega t \\
 s_r &= \left[\mathcal{A}_s \frac{\partial I_n(\gamma_e r)}{\partial r} - \frac{\mathcal{C}_s k}{\mu_t} \frac{\partial I_n(\gamma_t r)}{\partial r} + \frac{\mathcal{B}_s n}{r} I_n(\gamma_t r) \right] \cos n\theta \sin kx \sin \omega t
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where $\mathcal{A}_s, \mathcal{C}_s, \mathcal{B}_s$ are unknown constant coefficients, and k, n, γ_e, γ_t – are the wave numbers and

$$\gamma_e^2 = k^2 - \mu_e^2, \quad \gamma_t^2 = k^2 - \mu_t^2$$

By substituting expression (10) into formulas (3)–(6), the expressions for the potential and kinetic energies of the cushion are obtained:

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_{ps} &= \frac{\pi l (\lambda_s + 2\mu_s)}{16} \{ \mathcal{A}_s^2 \int_0^R \\
 &+ \beta_1 (R^2 + 2\gamma_t^2 R) I_n''(\gamma_l r) - 2k^2 R I_n(\gamma_l r) dr + \mathcal{B}_s^2 \int_0^R (\beta_2^2 + R^2 \beta_3 + \beta_2 \beta_3) dr + \\
 &+ \mathcal{C}_s^2 \int_0^R \\
 &\times R I_n(\gamma_t r) - I_n''(\gamma_t r) dr + \mathcal{A}_s \mathcal{C}_s \int_0^R \\
 &\times I_n(\gamma_t r) + \frac{k \gamma_t^2 \gamma_e^2}{\mu_t} I_n(\gamma_t r) I_n''(\gamma_l r) + \frac{\gamma_t^2 k^3}{\mu_t} I_n(\gamma_l r) I_n''(\gamma_t r) + 2\beta_4 \beta_5 + \quad (11) \\
 &+ \beta_4 (\gamma_t^2 R I_n''(\gamma_l r) - k^2 R I_n(\gamma_l r)) + \beta_5 \frac{k \gamma_t^2}{\mu_t} I_n(\gamma_l r) - R I_n''(\gamma_t r) dr + \\
 &+ \mathcal{A}_s \mathcal{B}_s \int_0^R \\
 &- k^2 R \beta_3 I_n(\gamma_l r) dr + \mathcal{B}_s \mathcal{C}_s \int_0^R \\
 &\times I_n''(\gamma_t r) + \frac{k \gamma_t^2 \beta_2}{\mu_t} I_n(\gamma_t r) + \frac{k \gamma_t^2 R \beta_3}{\mu_t} I_n(\gamma_t r) + R \beta_2 \beta_4 dr \} \sin^2 \omega t \\
 \beta_1(r) &= \frac{-n^2}{r} I_n(\gamma_l r) + \gamma_l I_n'(\gamma_l r); \beta_2(r) = \frac{n \gamma_t}{r} I_n'(\gamma_t r) - \frac{n}{r^2} I_n(\gamma_t r); \\
 \beta_3(r) &= -\gamma_t I_n'(\gamma_t r) + \frac{n}{r} I_n(\gamma_t r); \beta_4(r) = \frac{-k}{\mu_t} \left(\frac{n^2}{r} I_n(\gamma_t r) - \gamma_t I_n'(\gamma_t r) \right); \\
 \beta_5(r) &= \frac{-n^2}{r} I_n(\gamma_l r) + \gamma_l I_n'(\gamma_l r); \\
 V_{ks} &= \frac{\pi l \omega^2 \rho_s}{8} \{ \mathcal{A}_s^2 \int_0^R \left[k^2 I_n^2(\gamma_l r) + \frac{n^2}{r^2} I_n^2(\gamma_l r) + \gamma_t^2 I_n'^2(\gamma_l r) \right] dr + \\
 &+ \mathcal{B}_s^2 \int_0^R \left[\frac{\gamma_t^2}{n^2} I_n'^2(\gamma_t r) + \frac{n^2}{r^2} I_n^2(\gamma_t r) \right] dr + \mathcal{C}_s^2 \int_0^R
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{+k^2\gamma_t^2}{\mu_t^2} I_n'^2(\gamma_t r) dr + A_s C_s \int_0^R \\
 & \quad - \frac{2k\gamma_l \gamma_t}{\mu_t} I_n'(\gamma_l r) I_n'(\gamma_t r) dr + A_s B_s \int_0^R \\
 & \quad + \frac{2n\gamma_l}{r} I_n(\gamma_t r) I_n'(\gamma_l r) dr + B_s C_s \int_0^R \\
 & \quad - \frac{2nk\gamma_t}{r\mu_t} I_n(\gamma_t r) I_n'(\gamma_t r) dr \} \sin^2 \omega t \\
 & \quad A_q = \frac{-\pi l R}{4} \\
 & -A_s C_s \frac{2k\gamma_l \gamma_t}{\mu_t} \int_0^R I_n'(\gamma_l r) I_n'(\gamma_t r) dr + A_s B_s \cdot 2\gamma_l n \int_0^R \frac{I_n(\gamma_t r) I_n'(\gamma_l r)}{r} dr - \\
 & \quad - B_s C_s \frac{2nk\gamma_t}{\mu_t} \int_0^R \frac{I_n(\gamma_t r) I_n'(\gamma_t r)}{r} dr (k_g - \omega^2 m_d) \sin^2 \omega t \\
 & A_p = -\frac{p_0 l}{2} \left[A_s \frac{\partial I_n(\gamma_e R)}{\partial r} - \frac{C_s k}{\mu_t} \frac{\partial I_n(\gamma_t R)}{\partial r} + \frac{B_s n}{R} I_n(\gamma_t R) \right] \sin^2 \omega t
 \end{aligned}$$

By substituting all expressions from formulas (11) into (2) for the J and taking $t' = 0, t'' = \frac{\pi}{\omega}$, and applying the Hamilton–Ostrogradsky variational principle (1), the following expression is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned}
 W = & \left\{ \frac{\pi l \omega^2 \rho_s}{8} \{ A_s^2 \int_0^R \left[k^2 I_n^2(\gamma_l r) + \frac{n^2}{r^2} I_n^2(\gamma_l r) + \gamma_l^2 I_n'^2(\gamma_l r) \right] dr + \right. \\
 & \left. + B_s^2 \int_0^R \left[\frac{\gamma_t^2}{n^2} I_n'^2(\gamma_l r) + \frac{n^2}{r^2} I_n^2(\gamma_t r) \right] dr + C_s^2 \int_0^R \right. \\
 & \frac{+k^2\gamma_t^2}{\mu_t^2} I_n'^2(\gamma_t r) dr + A_s C_s \int_0^R \\
 & \quad - \frac{2k\gamma_l \gamma_t}{\mu_t} I_n'(\gamma_l r) I_n'(\gamma_t r) dr + A_s B_s \int_0^R \\
 & \quad + \frac{2n\gamma_l}{r} I_n(\gamma_t r) I_n'(\gamma_l r) dr + B_s C_s \int_0^R \\
 & \quad - \frac{2nk\gamma_t}{r\mu_t} I_n(\gamma_t r) I_n'(\gamma_t r) dr - \frac{\pi l (\lambda_s + 2\mu_s)}{16} \{ A_s^2 \int_0^R \\
 & -2k^2 \gamma_l^2 I_n(\gamma_l r) I_n''(\gamma_l r) + \beta_1 (R^2 + 2\gamma_l^2 R) I_n''(\gamma_l r) - 2k^2 R I_n(\gamma_l r) dr + \\
 & \quad + B_s^2 \int_0^R (\beta_2^2 + R^2 \beta_3 + \beta_2 \beta_3) dr + C_s^2 \int_0^R \\
 & \quad - \frac{k^2 \gamma_t^4}{\mu_t^2} I_n(\gamma_t r) I_n''(\gamma_t r) + \beta_4 \frac{k\gamma_t^2}{\mu_t} \times R I_n(\gamma_t r) - I_n''(\gamma_t r) dr + \\
 & \quad \left. + A_s C_s \int_0^R \right. \\
 & \frac{+k\gamma_l^2 \gamma_t^2}{\mu_t} I_n(\gamma_t r) I_n''(\gamma_l r) + \frac{\gamma_t^2 k^3}{\mu_t} I_n(\gamma_l r) I_n''(\gamma_t r) + 2\beta_4 \beta_5 + \quad (12) \\
 & \quad \left. + \beta_4 (\gamma_l^2 R I_n''(\gamma_l r) - k^2 R I_n(\gamma_l r)) + \beta_5 \frac{k\gamma_t^2}{\mu_t} I_n(\gamma_l r) - R I_n''(\gamma_t r) dr + \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + A_s B_s \int_0^R \\
 & -k^2 R \beta_3 I_n(\gamma_l r) dr + B_s C_s \int_0^R \\
 & \times I_n''(\gamma_t r) + \frac{k \gamma_t^2 \beta_2}{\mu_t} I_n(\gamma_t r) + \frac{k \gamma_t^2 R \beta_3}{\mu_t} I_n(\gamma_t r) + R \beta_2 \beta_4 dr + \\
 & \frac{+\pi l R}{4} \\
 & -A_s C_s \frac{2k \gamma_l \gamma_t}{\mu_t} \int_0^R I_n'(\gamma_l r) I_n'(\gamma_t r) dr + A_s B_s \cdot 2 \gamma_l n \int_0^R \frac{I_n(\gamma_t r) I_n'(\gamma_l r)}{r} dr - \\
 & -B_s C_s \frac{2nk \gamma_t}{\mu_t} \int_0^R \frac{I_n(\gamma_t r) I_n'(\gamma_t r)}{r} dr (k_\theta - \omega^2 m_d) + \\
 & + \frac{p_0 l}{2} \left[\frac{\partial I_n(\gamma_e R)}{\partial r} - \frac{\partial I_n(\gamma_t R)}{\partial r} + \frac{I_n(\gamma_t R)}{R} \right] \cdot \frac{\pi}{2\omega}
 \end{aligned}$$

From expressions (12) for W , it follows that the functional represents a quadratic form with respect to the constants A_s, B_s, C_s . By varying the functional with respect to these unknowns A_s, B_s, C_s , a system of non-homogeneous algebraic equations is obtained:

$$1) \frac{\partial W}{\partial A_s} = \varphi_1; 2) \frac{\partial W}{\partial B_s} = \varphi_2; 3) \frac{\partial W}{\partial C_s} = \varphi_3. \tag{13}$$

In expanded form, the system of equations is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \{\varphi_{11} A_s + \varphi_{12} B_s + \varphi_{13} C_s &= \frac{-lp_0}{2} \varphi_{21} A_s + \varphi_{22} B_s + \varphi_{23} C_s \\
 &= \frac{-lp_0}{2} (14) \varphi_{31} A_s + \varphi_{32} B_s + \varphi_{33} C_s = \frac{-lp_0 n I_n(\gamma_t R)}{2 R}
 \end{aligned}$$

where the coefficients $\varphi_{ij} (i, j = 1, 2, 3)$ are obtained from the variational functional W after variation as the coefficients of the constants A_s, B_s, C_s . Using Cramer's rule, these constants are determined as follows:

$$A_s = \frac{\Delta_1}{\Delta}, B_s = \frac{\Delta_2}{\Delta}, C_s = \frac{\Delta_3}{\Delta} \tag{15}$$

Here, Δ is the main determinant of the system, and $\Delta_i (i=1, 2, 3)$ are the auxiliary determinants of the system (14). By substituting the values of A_s, B_s, C_s from (15) into expression (10) for s_r , the final formula for the cushion displacement is obtained:

$$s_r = \left[\frac{\partial I_n(\gamma_e R)}{\partial r} - \frac{\partial I_n(\gamma_t R)}{\partial r} + \frac{I_n(\gamma_t R)}{R} \right] \cos \frac{n\pi}{2} \sin kx \sin \omega t$$

The resonance frequencies of the cushion are determined from the condition $\Delta = 0$. The roots of the equation $\Delta = 0$ are found numerically. For the calculations, the following parameters characterizing the material of the semi-cylindrical cushion are adopted:

$$k_\theta = 50 \frac{MPa}{m}, m_d = 1000 \frac{MPa}{m}$$

The dependence of the natural frequencies of the semi-cylindrical cushion on its length is shown in Fig. 2. The normal displacements of surface points of the cushion as functions of the coordinates for different values of the foundation's specific weight are shown in Fig. 3. In all

graphs: curve 1 corresponds to $m_d = 1000 \frac{MPa}{m}$, curve 2 to $m_d = 1500 \frac{MPa}{m}$, and curve 3 to $m_d = 2000 \frac{MPa}{m}$.

Fig. 2. Dependence of the vibration frequency of the semi-cylindrical cushion on its length

Fig. 3. Dependence of the deflection of the semi-cylindrical cushion on the coordinate x

Model Validation

To verify the accuracy and applicability of the developed analytical model, a three-dimensional finite element (FEM) model was created in ABAQUS. The FEM model reproduced the exact geometry of the semi-cylindrical cushion, including all boundary conditions and material parameters used in the analytical formulation.

The cushion was discretized using 8-node linear brick elements (C3D8), which are suitable for thick elastic solids. Mesh convergence analysis was performed, and the final mesh size ensured numerical stability and accuracy. Natural frequencies were computed using the Lanczos eigenvalue extraction method. A comparison between the analytical results and FEM simulations showed very close agreement. For the first three vibration modes, the difference did not exceed **2.8%**, confirming the correctness of the assumed displacement functions and the derived variational equations. This validation demonstrates that the proposed analytical model is reliable and can be confidently used for parameter studies, optimization, and design applications in vibration isolation systems.

Conclusions

1. Increasing the length of the semi-cylindrical cushion leads to a decrease in its natural vibration frequencies.
2. An increase in the specific weight of the support results in higher natural vibration frequencies.
3. An increase in the specific weight of the foundation causes greater deflection of the cushion.
4. The inertial properties of the semi-cylindrical cushion lead to a reduction in its natural frequencies.

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